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Obligation of the Enterprise Tenant to Accept the Enterprise

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***Annotation:** This article analyzes the issues of accepting and using a business under a lease agreement. The lessee is obligated to accept the business within the stipulated time frame according to the contract terms, and delays or refusals in this process can cause significant harm to the lessor. The lessee must utilize the property in accordance with their obligations and fulfill the contract terms. Otherwise, this situation can lead to the cessation of the business's operations and the loss of clients and business relationships. The lessee is also required to use the business without altering its type of activity; otherwise, the essence of the contract may be lost. The article also provides information about the lessee's responsibilities and the lessor's rights to terminate the contract.*

***Key words:** Lease agreement, Business acceptance, Lessee obligations, Lessor rights, Property usage, Contract terms, Operational cessation, Client relationships, Business activities, Contract termination.*

The obligations of the lessee under the lease agreement to accept the enterprise and use the enterprise in accordance with the terms of the contract, if such conditions are not specified in the contract - in accordance with the purpose of the property, are of particular importance and arise from the nature of the object being leased.

The lessee is obliged to accept the enterprise within the period stipulated by the contract. Unlike other objects of property rental, failure to receive the enterprise by the lessee on time or not receiving it at all can cause significant damage to the lessor and even lead to the destruction of the enterprise. This situation may arise if the owner of the enterprise is unable to exploit it himself for any reason. For example, if a person who inherited the enterprise participates as a lessor under the contract and does not have experience in the field of entrepreneurial activity. In this case, if the object of the heir of the enterprise is to preserve it as a functioning economic unit, it is first of all naturally interested in

transferring the enterprise to a person who can continue the work of the heir.¹ In this situation, delaying the adoption of the enterprise can lead to negative consequences, including the loss of customers, the collapse of business relations, and even the liquidation of the enterprise.

In this case, if the impossibility of transferring the enterprise occurs at the fault of the lessee, for example, due to the delay or non-obtaining by the lessee of the license necessary for the activity on the basis of the leased enterprise, the consequences of the delay in the execution of the creditor shall be applied (Article 338 of the Civil Code of Uzbekistan). In other words, the lessor has the right to demand compensation for losses caused by the delay in the transfer of the enterprise. In this case, in accordance with part 3 of Article 333 of the Civil Code of the Republic of Uzbekistan, the lessee, as a person carrying out entrepreneurial activity, is liable if he does not prove that it was impossible to properly fulfill the obligation due to an irresistible force, that is, due to emergency and unavoidable circumstances (force majeure).

According to Article 551 of the Civil Code of the Republic of Uzbekistan, the lease holder's delay in accepting the object of lease is not a basis for early termination of the lease agreement at the request of the lessor. However, Part 2 of Article 382 of the Civil Code allows the parties to establish additional grounds for early termination of the contract. In this situation, i.e., in the event of the tenant's refusal to properly fulfill the obligation (i.e., to transfer the enterprise) provided by the lessor, the lessor's right to demand the termination of the contract must be clearly indicated in the process of signing the contract.

The lessee must use the enterprise in accordance with the terms of the contract, if such terms are not specified in the contract - in accordance with the purpose of the property (Part 1 of Article 545 of the Criminal Code of the Republic of Uzbekistan)². If, despite the written notice from the lessor, the lessee uses the property in violation of the terms of the contract or the purpose of the property, the lessor has the right to demand early termination of the contract and compensation for damages (Part 2 of Article 545, Clause 1 of Part 1 of Article 551 of the Civil Code of the Republic of Uzbekistan)³.

There is a perspective in legal literature that the use of leased property should not be considered an obligation of the lessee, as it is the lessee who has an interest in utilizing the leased property. In particular, S.B. Bobokulov, while commenting on Article 545 of the Civil Code of the Republic of Uzbekistan, expresses the following opinion: "The use of property defines the main essence of the lease agreement. For this reason, the law imposes requirements on the lessee regarding the use of leased property, and these requirements are aimed at ensuring the preservation of the property and the protection of the lessor's interests. The use of leased property must be carried out in accordance with the contract."⁴ According to V.V. Vitryansky, in Article 615 of the Civil Code of the Russian Federation (corresponding to Article 545 of the Civil Code of the Republic of Uzbekistan), the legislator emphasizes not the word "use," but rather that the use of property must comply with the terms of the contract or the intended purpose of the property. The author justifies his viewpoint as follows: "Negative consequences arise not in cases where the lessee fails to use the leased property,

¹ Комментарий к части третьей ГК РФ / Исслед. центр частного права; под ред. А.Л. Маковского, Е.А. Суханова. - М.: Юристъ. 2003. - С. 285.

² <https://lex.uz/docs/180552#184407>

³ <https://lex.uz/docs/180552#184407>

⁴ Ўзбекистон Республикасининг фуқаролик кодексига шарҳ: Профессинал шарҳлар. Т 2./Ўзбекистон Республикаси Адлия вазирлиги. — Тошкент: Vaktria press, 2013. 279-бет.

but when the leased property is used in a manner inconsistent with the terms of the contract or the intended purpose of the property."⁵

Indeed, according to current legislation, most objects that can be leased, such as buildings, structures, equipment, and vehicles, do not incur significant negative consequences if the lessee properly fulfills their obligations to pay rent and maintain the property in good condition. On the other hand, it is not beneficial for the tenant to receive income without using the property while still incurring expenses..⁶

Regarding an enterprise as an object of lease, failure to use it can lead to serious losses for the lessor and even the loss of the enterprise. This is because the mandatory elements of any enterprise are the property rights and obligations related to its activities. It is precisely due to these elements that the enterprise exists in an organizational aspect (for example, relationships with partners and consumers of produced goods), i.e., it has the ability to function normally. Failure to carry out entrepreneurial activity based on the leased property complex may lead to the loss of existing legal and factual relationships with the lessor. The loss of property relations connected to the enterprise's activities can lead to the suspension of its operations and its transformation into a simple property complex.

In addition, non-use of the leased enterprise can result in negative consequences for its material structure. For example, if a livestock complex is leased, the main property that enables economic activity is a certain number of livestock. The tenant's failure to use such a complex even for a short period can lead to a decrease in the number of cattle, spoilage of feed, and consequently, to a serious disruption of the enterprise's operations.

Based on the above, it should be emphasized that the lessee not only has the right but also the obligation to operate the enterprise entrusted to them.⁷ Otherwise, the enterprise loses its value. It should be noted, however, that in some cases, temporarily suspending the enterprise's activities may be beneficial for the lessee. For example, when there is no demand for the goods being produced. Nevertheless, such a suspension of the enterprise's activities should be temporary and should allow the entrepreneur to resume operations based on the enterprise. This does not mean starting the enterprise's operations from scratch.

If the lessee is not utilizing the leased enterprise, the lessor has the right to demand early termination of the contract on the grounds that the lessee is significantly deteriorating the property, in accordance with paragraph 2 of part 1 of Article 551 of the Civil Code of the Republic of Uzbekistan. The lessee must operate the enterprise without altering its type of activity⁸. In this case, the lessee of an enterprise established by the owner for conducting a specific type of activity cannot arbitrarily change it to another type of activity.

In conclusion, it can be said that accepting the enterprise is one of the crucial obligations of the lessee, and its non-fulfillment or delay in accepting the enterprise can lead to negative consequences, including the loss of clients, the breakdown of business relationships, and even the termination of the enterprise's operations. Furthermore, the lessee must use the enterprise in accordance with the terms of the contract, or if such terms are not specified in the contract, in accordance with the purpose of the property. In other words, the lessee must use the enterprise without altering its type of activity. Otherwise, the lease agreement for the enterprise loses its essence.

⁵ Витрянский В.В. Договор аренды и его виды: прокат, фрахтование на время, аренда зданий; сооружений и предприятий, лизинг. (Изд. 2-е, испр.) - М.: «Статут», 2000. - С. 114.

⁶ Ёрш А.В, Аренда зданий и иных сооружений. Дис. ... канд. юрид. наук. - М., 2003. - С. 152.

⁷ Каранг: Шершеневич Г.Ф. Курс торгового права. Т. I: Введение. Торговые деятели. - М.: Статут, 2005. - С. 181.

⁸ Шершеневич Г.Ф. Курс торгового права. Т. I: Введение. Торговые деятели. - М.: Статут, 2005. - С. 181.

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